

AWT Daily Survey

Start of Block: Controle

Q16 Welcome to today's survey! Please answer the following questions.

Location Where did you work today?

- At the office
 - At home
 - Other
 - Combination of home and at the office/somewhere else
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QEEW Please answer the following questions about today's workday. To what extent...

	Not at all	To a small extent	To some extent	To a large extent	To a very large extent
...did significant changes occur in your work compared to the previous period?	<input type="radio"/>				
...were you able to leave your work area to chat with a colleague?	<input type="radio"/>				
...did you have contact with colleagues as part of your work?	<input type="radio"/>				
...were you able to chat with colleagues during working hours?	<input type="radio"/>				
...were you able to interrupt your work for a short time when you felt it was necessary?	<input type="radio"/>				
...could you personally decide how much time you needed for a specific activity?	<input type="radio"/>				

...were you able to organize your work yourself?

...did you work overtime?

...were you able to complete tasks without being interrupted?

...did you experience disruptions while working?

...could you decide your own start and end time for your working day?

...did you have to do the same things repeatedly in your work?

...was your work varied?

...did you have enough variety in your work?

Plan_overtime Do you plan to work overtime this evening?

Yes

No

Open Is there anything else you want to share about today? (optional)

End of Block: Controle
